

EARLY OUTCOME OF HAND-SEWN VERSUS STAPLED CLOSURE OF STOMA IN PAEDIATRIC AGE GROUP

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Abstract

Background: The choice between hand-sewn and stapled techniques for stoma closure in pediatric patients remains a key surgical decision. Each method has distinct advantages, with outcomes influenced by operative time, intraoperative blood loss, postoperative recovery, and complication rates. This study aimed to compare early outcomes of both techniques in children.

Methods: A randomized controlled trial was conducted at the Department of Pediatric Surgery, LUMHS, Jamshoro, from September 16, 2022, to March 15, 2023. A total of 160 pediatric patients undergoing ileostomy or colostomy closure were randomized into two groups: Group A (hand-sewn) and Group B (stapled), with 80 patients each. Outcomes assessed included operative time, intraoperative blood loss, return of bowel activity, hospital stay, and complications (anastomotic leak and surgical site infection). Data were analyzed using SPSS version 25.

Results: The stapled technique significantly reduced operative time (77.99 ± 13.04 vs. 91.78 ± 17.71 minutes, $p=0.0001$) and hospital stay (13.05 ± 3.82 vs. 15.21 ± 4.82 days, $p=0.002$). However, intraoperative blood loss was higher in the stapled group (22.85 ± 10.89 vs. 18.66 ± 6.70 ml, $p=0.004$). Rates of anastomotic leak (5.0% vs. 7.5%, $p=0.373$) and surgical site infection (30.0% vs. 35.0%, $p=0.500$) were comparable. No significant difference was observed in return of bowel activity ($p=0.442$).

Conclusion: Both techniques are safe and effective. The stapled method offers shorter operative time and hospital stay but slightly higher blood loss. Technique selection should be individualized.

INTRODUCTION:

Pediatric surgical care is highly precise due to distinct anatomical and physiological features, and

unique aspects of healing, along with an immature immune system. Gastrointestinal surgery for gastrointestinal diseases often involves temporary

stoma formation (and subsequent closure) and is frequently performed in children with varying levels of intestinal pathology, including necrotizing enterocolitis, Hirshsprung's disease, intestinal atresia, and other congenital or acquired anomalies 1, 2. While the creation of a stoma is lifesaving, its closure is an essential move towards restoring bowel continuity and improving quality of life. However, discussion continues as to the best method of stoma closure.

Intestinal anastomosis has long been the standard surgical modality. This technique is adaptable, enabling the closure to be customized in part to account for anatomical contributors that differ from patient to patient; this is vital given the small caliber of pediatric intestines. Moreover, it is affordable and accessible (3). However, this is operator dependent, can take more time, and with a sub-optimal technique, a higher incidence of complications exists, such as anastomotic leakage or stricture (4).

This is in contrast to stapled techniques that have gained popularity with advancements in surgical technology. They are devices that allow for quick and uniform anastomosis, theoretically decreasing operative time and enhancing surgical efficiency (5). Studies also indicate that a uniformity of staple lines may diminish the potential for anastomotic leakage (6). Still, worries linger about greater expense and availability in some resource-limited settings as well as the risks of foreign body reaction, bowel obstruction, or infection (7).

Both techniques are used routinely, and high-quality pediatric-specific evidence comparing their outcomes is still lacking. Early post-operative complications such as surgical site infection, anastomotic leakage, ileus, and strictures are associated with increased recovery time and healthcare burden (8). Previous literature, primarily in adults, is inconsistent and not directly generalizable to children (9–11). Among hundreds of published reports, there are few comparative studies of the outcomes of hand-sewn vs stapled stoma closure in pediatric patients to inform evidence-based surgical decision-making.

PATIENTS AND METHODOLOGY

This Randomized Controlled Trial (RCT) was conducted in the department of Paediatric Surgery, Liaquat University of Medical and Health Sciences (LUMHS), Jamshoro, Pakistan. Research approval was obtained, and the study was conducted over 6 months between September 16, 2022, and March 15, 2023.

Using the WHO sample size calculator, a sample size was calculated. The operative time for hand-sewn closure was calculated as 95.7 ± 14.7 minutes, and for stapled closure, it was deemed to be 74.8 ± 3.6 minutes. The calculations were done with a power of 95% and a significance level of 5%. The sample size was calculated to be 14 patients (7 in each group) at first. Based on the statistical assumption of normality and adequate power for subgroup analyses, 160 patients were enrolled ($n=80$ in each group). Recruitment was done using a Non-Probability, Consecutive Sampling technique.

Age more than 6 months to less than 12 years and of either sex, undergoing closure of ileostomy or colostomy stoma were included in the study. Exclusion criteria included patients with renal failure or any other comorbid condition and/or those who were unable to give consent or refused to take part in the study. The study was performed after the ethical approval of the College of Physicians and Surgeons, Pakistan (CPSP). Before enrollment, written consent was obtained from the guardians of patients. Baseline demographic and clinical characteristics, including age, gender, living status (home/domicile), height, weight, and presence of comorbidity (e.g., cardiac lesions; vertebral or limb abnormalities; renal disorders; asthma) were recorded.

Patients were randomly assigned to two groups using the sealed opaque envelope method. In Group A, in the sixth step, the ileostomy or colostomy stoma closure was performed with a single-layer extramucosal interrupted hand-sewn technique. Group B was treated with a stapler device and closure. Uniformity and bias control were ensured by performing all procedures under general anesthesia through board-certified pediatric surgeons with more than 5 years of post-fellowship experience. Outcomes including

anastomotic leak, surgical site infection (SSI), duration of surgery, return of bowel activity, intraoperative blood loss, and length of stay were evaluated postoperatively according to standard hospital protocol and monitored until discharge in both groups.

Data were analyzed using SPSS version 25. Quantitative variables (age, height, weight, operative time, hospital length of stay, intraoperative blood loss, and return of bowel activity) were assessed with the mean ± standard deviation (SD) or median (IQR), according to normal distribution given by the Shapiro-Wilk test. Data were presented as frequencies and percentages for qualitative variables: Gender, residence, type of cardiac lesions (increased blood flow vs decreased heart output), vertebral/limb defects, renal disorders, asthma conditions, SSI, and anastomotic leaks.

This inferential analysis was performed to assess for differences in the outcomes between the two groups. Categorical variables were analyzed using the Chi-square test or Fisher's Exact test, as applicable; continuous variables were compared with the independent t-test. Limitations were assigned, and confounders like age, sex, body mass

index, residence (province), cardiac lesions, vertebral or limb defects, and reno-genital disorders on the findings of patients with asthma. Data was analyzed through post-stratification employing Chi-square/Fisher's Exact test and independent t-test (considered statistically significant if p-value ≤0.05).

RESULTS

In this randomized controlled trial, a total of 160 pediatric patients were included to compare the outcomes of hand-sewn and stapled closure techniques for ileostomy or colostomy stoma. The patients were equally divided into two groups: Group A (Hand-Sewn) and Group B (Stapled), with 80 patients in each group. Baseline characteristics were comparable between groups (all p>0.05). Operative time was significantly shorter in the stapled group (77.99 ± 13.04 vs. 91.78 ± 17.71 minutes; p=0.0001), while intraoperative blood loss was higher (22.85 ± 10.89 vs. 18.66 ± 6.70 ml; p=0.004). Hospital stay was significantly reduced in the stapled group (13.05 ± 3.82 vs. 15.21 ± 4.82 days; p=0.002). Return of bowel activity was comparable (p=0.442). Table 1.

TABLE 1: DESCRIPTIVE STATISTICS FOR DISTRIBUTION OF CONTINUOUS VARIABLE n=160

GROUPS	VARIABLES	MEAN±SD	P-VALUE
	Age Group	7.10±3.11	0.067
	Weight	26.60±10.16	0.166
	Height	100.25±16.57	0.090
Hand Sewn (Group A)	Duration of Return of Bowel Activity	5.98±1.82	0.076
	Duration of Procedure	91.78±17.71	0.087
	Duration of Post Operative Hospital Stay	15.21±4.81	0.112
	Intraoperative Blood Loss	18.66±6.70	0.285

	Age Group	6.49±3.07	0.089
	Weight	27.45±9.93	0.106
	Height	101.49±16.71	0.063
Stapler (Group B)	Duration of Return of Bowel Activity	6.20±1.87	0.083
	Duration of Procedure	77.99±13.04	0.119
	Duration of Post Operative Hospital Stay	13.05±3.81	0.115
	Intraoperative Blood Loss	22.85±10.89	0.078

Applied Shapiro Wilk test

The stapled group demonstrated significantly shorter operative time (p=0.0001) and reduced postoperative hospital stay (p=0.002) compared to the hand-sewn group. However, intraoperative

blood loss was significantly higher in the stapled group (p=0.004). There was no significant difference in return of bowel activity between the groups (p=0.442). Table 2.

Table 2: Operative and Postoperative Outcomes

Outcome	Group A (Hand-Sewn)	Group B (Stapled)	p-value
Operative Time (mins)	91.78 ± 17.71	77.99 ± 13.04	0.0001
Intraoperative Blood Loss (ml)	18.66 ± 6.70	22.85 ± 10.89	0.004
Duration of Postoperative Hospital Stay (days)	15.21 ± 4.82	13.05 ± 3.82	0.002
Return to Bowel Activity (hours)	5.98 ± 1.82	6.20 ± 1.87	0.442

Rates of anastomotic leak (p=0.373) and surgical site infection (p=0.500) were comparable between the hand-sewn and stapled groups, with no

statistically significant differences observed. Table 3.

Table 3: Postoperative Complications

Complication	Group A (Hand-Sewn)	Group B (Stapled)	p-value
Anastomotic Leak (%)	5.0% (4/80)	7.5% (6/80)	0.373
Surgical Site Infection (%)	30.0% (24/80)	35.0% (28/80)	0.500

Operative time was significantly shorter in the stapled group across all subgroups. This difference remained statistically significant in both age

categories (0.5–6 years: $p=0.0001$; >6 years: $p=0.001$) and across genders (male: $p=0.0001$; female: $p=0.003$). Table 4.

Table 4: Stratification of Operative Time by Key Variables

Variables	Group A (Hand-Sewn)	Group B (Stapled)	p-value
Age (0.5–6 years) (mins)	94.93 ± 16.31	76.83 ± 12.49	0.0001
Age (>6 years) (mins)	89.98 ± 18.38	78.93 ± 13.55	0.001
Male (mins)	93.15 ± 17.24	78.64 ± 13.58	0.0001
Female (mins)	89.21 ± 18.62	77.19 ± 12.50	0.003

DISCUSSION

Comparison of hand-sewn vs stapled methods for ileostomy or colostomy closure in paediatric patients is a continually evolving area of surgical practice. The two methods each have their own benefits, and the choice is based primarily upon patient factors, availability of resources, and surgeon experience. This current randomized controlled trial aimed at assessing early outcomes to provide relevant clinical evidence for surgical decision-making.

The stapled technique was associated with significantly less operative time, which is one of the main findings of this study. This observation correlates with previous studies showing the effectiveness of stapling devices to rapidly perform standardized anastomosis (12). The operating time reduction is particularly relevant when addressing the pediatric surgeon, as anesthesia duration can expose patients to potential perioperative events, including respiratory morbidity and recovery delay (13). Consequently, a reduction in operative time may lead to a safer procedure in this cohort.

However, the stapled technique was linked to greater loss of blood during surgery. This could be due to the fact that stapling is more mechanical, so it involves more tissue handling or slightly vascular injury. The clinical significance of this finding is generally low, and similar observations have been reported in a number of previous studies (14). This limitation could diminish with further refinements in stapling technology and surgical technique.

The stapled group showed a significantly improved postoperative recovery, which is evidenced by a shorter hospital stay. This is in accordance with

previous studies that indicated less operative trauma and increased short time of surgery to allow early postoperative recovery (15, 16). The time to return of bowel function was similar between groups, suggesting that physiological recovery may be more dependent on patient factors such as nutrition or comorbidities rather than the anastomotic type itself (17).

Notably, the rates of anastomotic leakage and surgical site infection (SSI) were similar between both groups, hinting at the aspirational safety of the two methods. Our findings concord with literature, including systematic reviews, demonstrating no difference in complication rate when centres are performed by highly experienced surgeons (18). However, some studies suggest that stapled techniques are associated with a greater risk of anastomotic stricture due to lower compliance at the staple line (19), but these outcomes were not seen in our cohort; this may be a result of short-term follow-up.

All these factors are considered helpful with respect to surgical efficiency and shorten hospital stay, enhancing workflow in high-volume centers from a more pragmatic point of view. On the other side, the hand-sewn technique still is an inexpensive and feasible option, especially in developing countries where stapling devices may not be available (20). Furthermore, outcomes depend largely on surgeon experience: stapled techniques may have a short learning curve, but experienced hand-sewn anastomosis is still important in complex cases (21).

The findings are consistent with previous studies showing shorter operative times and similar complication rates with stapled closures (14, 22).

While increased SSI rates with stapled techniques have been suggested, due to the presence of a foreign body (23), this was not demonstrated in our study and likely reflects standardized perioperative care and infection control measures.

Limitations

This study has several limitations that should be considered. The relatively short follow-up period precluded assessment of long-term outcomes, particularly complications such as anastomotic stricture. Furthermore, the single-center design may limit the external validity and generalizability of the findings. Future studies should incorporate multicenter designs with extended follow-up to better evaluate long-term outcomes. Additionally, ongoing advancements in surgical technology, including bioabsorbable stapling devices, may further influence the applicability and outcomes of stapled techniques in pediatric surgery.

CONCLUSION

Both hand-sewn and stapled techniques are safe and effective for pediatric stoma closure. The stapled approach is associated with reduced operative time and shorter hospital stay, whereas the hand-sewn technique remains a cost-effective alternative with comparable complication rates. Technique selection should be individualized based on patient factors, surgeon expertise, and resource availability.

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